

Protection of Artistic Works in the Information Communication Technology Era in Tanzania: An Appraisal of the Legal Framework

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Abstract:

The rapid advancement of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) has transformed the creation, distribution, and commercialization of artistic works globally. In Tanzania, while the legal framework for copyright protection exists, it faces significant challenges in adapting to the digital environment. This article examines the adequacy of Tanzania's legal regime in protecting artistic works in the ICT era, focusing on key statutes such as the Copyright and Neighbouring Rights Act, the Cybercrimes Act, and the Electronic Transactions Act. It also highlights institutional and policy weaknesses, including the absence of digital-specific provisions, weak enforcement mechanisms, and limited public awareness. The article concludes by proposing reforms to strengthen the protection of artistic works, promote compliance with international treaties, and enhance institutional capacity to safeguard creators' rights in the digital age. In conducting this study, the author employed documentary review to get insight from other others. Finally, the author provides recommendations to curb the identified challenges.

Keywords: Artistic Works, Copyright Protection, ICT Era, Tanzania.

Suggested Citation: E. B. Msambazi & K. Gamba (2025), 'Protection of Artistic Works in the Information and Communication Technology Era in Tanzania: An Appraisal of the Legal Framework,' *TzJMS*. Vol. 4. No. 1. pp. 34-44.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Artistic works form a vital part of Tanzania's cultural heritage and creative economy. They embody the intellectual and emotional expression of individuals and communities through visual arts, music, film, literature, and other forms of creative expression. Beyond their cultural significance, artistic works also contribute substantially to economic development by generating employment, promoting tourism, and enhancing national identity. However, the growth of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) has fundamentally transformed the way artistic works are created, distributed, and consumed. The digital environment has expanded opportunities for Tanzanian artists to showcase their creativity to global audiences but has simultaneously exposed them to new and complex challenges, particularly in relation to copyright protection and enforcement. The advent of digital platforms such as YouTube, TikTok, Instagram, and Boomplay has eased access to creative works, enabling creators to share their art instantly and reach consumers without the constraints of traditional distribution channels. Yet, these same platforms have amplified the risks of unauthorized reproduction, modification, and dissemination of artistic works, often without the consent or compensation of the original creators. Such practices undermine the moral and economic rights of artists and weaken the creative industry's potential to thrive in the digital economy.

2. LEGAL MATERIALS AND METHODS

This article employs the doctrinal research methodology to analyze the primary and secondary sources of legal materials to appraise the regime for the protection of artistic works in Tanzania. The primary sources include the Constitution of Tanzania, the Copyright and Neighbouring Rights Act, the Tanzania Communications Regulatory Authority Act, and several other legislations whose operations affect artistic works. A review of judicial decisions and academic materials is also undertaken.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 The concept of artistic works

Artistic works refers to any production in the literary, scientific and artistic domain, whatever may be the mode or form of its expression, such as books, pamphlets and other writings. This includes works such as lectures, sermons, dramatic or musical works, choreographic performances, musical compositions, cinematographic works, drawings, paintings, sculptures, engravings, photographic works, applied art, and illustrations related to geography, architecture, or science. These are all protected under copyright as creative expressions.¹

¹ Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works (adopted on 1974 and amended on September 28, 1979, entered into force July, 25 1994) art. 2(1).

Artistic work qualifies as an intangible asset because it is identifiable, separable and the potential value that can be accurately measured.² In this regard, artistic work is a copyright material that attracts legal protection. In Tanzania artistic works are covered under section 8 of the Copyright and Neighboring Rights Act which states that copyright in a literary and artistic work comprises the exclusive economic and moral rights of the author.³ Artistic works can be created through online platforms, and customers can access them through those platforms facilitated by the infrastructures of ICT.⁴

The Copyright and Neighbouring Rights Act in section 5 (2) provides as follows:

In this section, literary and artistic works shall include in particular (a) books, pamphlets and other writings, including computer programs; (b) lectures, addresses, sermons and other works of the same nature; (c) dramatic and dramatic musical works; (d) musical works (vocal and instrumental), whether or not they include accompanying words; (e) choreographic works and pantomimes; (f) cinematographic works, and other audio-visual works; (g) works of drawing, painting, architecture, sculpture, engraving, lithography and tapestry; (h) photographic works including works expressed by processes analogous to photography; (i) works of applied art, whether handicraft or produced on an industrial scale; and (j) illustrations, maps, plans, sketches and three dimensional works relative to geography, topography, architecture or science.

Although the protection of artistic works is provided under legislations, the judiciary continues to play an important role in protecting copyrights. The courts have been invited to pronounce on the rights and liabilities of parties when there are infringements. The case of *Hamis Mwinjuma and Ambwene Yesaya v Tigo Company Ltd*⁵ shows how the court has a duty to protect the creators of the artistic works against infringements in Tanzania. In this case the plaintiffs sued the defendant for copyright infringements for the authorized use of ringtone of the music created by the plaintiffs. In *Tanzania-China Friendship Textile Company Ltd vs Nida Textile Mills (T) Ltd (NIDA)*, besides holding that an artistic work is a copyright, the court awarded damages in the sum of 150 000 000

²<<https://www.google.com/search?q=artistic+works+copyright&sca>> accessed on 12th May 2024

³ Cap. 218 [RE 2002].

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ *Hamisi Mwinjuma and Ambwene Yesaya v. Tigo Company Ltd*, Civil Case No. 38 of 2011, High Court of Tanzania at Dar es Salaam (Unreported).

Tanzanian Shillings to the plaintiff who had suffered harm by the infringement of his copyright by the defendant.⁶

3.2 Legal framework for protecting artistic works in Tanzania

The protection of artistic works in Tanzania is governed by a combination of constitutional, statutory, and institutional instruments that collectively safeguard the rights of creators and promote the growth of the creative industry. Although these laws provide a foundation for intellectual property protection, their effectiveness in the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) era depends on how well they adapt to the challenges of digital creation, distribution, and enforcement.

Tanzania is a member of the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) and the African Regional Intellectual Property Organization (ARIPO), both of which promote cooperation in intellectual property protection. However, the country has not yet ratified key treaties such as the WIPO Performances and Phonograms Treaty (1996) and the WIPO Copyright Treaty (1996)—commonly known as the “Internet Treaties.” These treaties are designed to address copyright issues in digital networks, including the reproduction and distribution of works online.

Similarly, Tanzania has signed but not ratified the ARIPO Kampala Protocol on Voluntary Registration of Copyright and Related Rights (2021), which would enhance regional cooperation in protecting creative works. Ratifying and domesticating these instruments would strengthen Tanzania’s ability to combat cross-border digital piracy and align its laws with global best practices in the ICT era.

3.2.1 The constitution

The Constitution of the United Republic of Tanzania, 1977 forms the supreme legal basis for all laws in the country and guarantees the protection of property rights, including intellectual property. Article 24 of the Constitution provides that every person is entitled to own property and to the protection of that property in accordance with the law.⁷ Artistic works, as a form of intellectual property, therefore fall under this constitutional protection. This means that any unauthorized use, reproduction, or distribution of an artist’s work constitutes a deprivation of property, which is unlawful unless done under the authority of the law and with fair compensation.

The Constitution further upholds the right to work and to be remunerated according to one’s effort and qualifications. For artists, this implies a constitutional entitlement to earn from their creative labor, reinforcing the need for legal frameworks that protect artistic

⁶ (Civil Case 106 of 2020) [2022] TZHC 13134 (28 September 2022) [[2022\] TZHC 13134](#) Accessed on 19th November 2025.

⁷ Article 24 of the Constitution of the United, Republic of Tanzania.

works from exploitation—both offline and in digital environments. Thus, the constitutional principles of property ownership and fair compensation provide the normative foundation for the protection of artistic works in Tanzania’s ICT era.

3.2.2 The Copyright and Neighbouring Rights Act, Cap. 218 [RE 2023]

The Copyright and Neighbouring Rights Act is the primary legislation governing the protection of artistic works in Tanzania. The Act protects a wide range of creative expressions, including literary, musical, dramatic, artistic, and folkloric works. Under section 5(1), authors of original artistic works are automatically entitled to copyright protection from the moment of creation, without the need for registration.⁸ The Act grants creators both moral rights such as the right to be identified as the author and to preserve the integrity of the work and economic rights, which include the right to reproduce, distribute, and communicate their works to the public. It also provides civil and criminal remedies for infringement, including injunctions, damages, and the confiscation of infringing copies.

To administer and enforce copyright, the Act established the Copyright Society of Tanzania (COSOTA). COSOTA’s primary functions include licensing, collecting royalties, protecting the interests of copyright holders, and representing them in national and international matters.⁹ However, while the Act provides strong theoretical protection, it lacks explicit provisions dealing with online or digital infringement—an omission that limits its practical application in the ICT era, where artistic works are frequently disseminated and monetized through digital platforms.

3.2.3 Tanzania Communications Regulatory Authority Act, No. 12 of 2003

The Tanzania Communications Regulatory Authority (TCRA) was established under this Act to regulate communications, broadcasting, and online content within Tanzania.¹⁰ In the context of artistic works, TCRA plays a crucial role in overseeing online media and ensuring that content providers comply with national laws, including copyright regulations.¹¹

Through its Online Content Regulations, TCRA can monitor, investigate, and take action against the distribution of unlawful or pirated digital content.¹² The Authority also promotes public awareness about responsible online behavior, which indirectly supports the protection of artistic works against unauthorized use and distribution. However, its mandate focuses more on regulating communications than on intellectual property

⁸ Copyright and Neighboring Rights Act, Cap. 218.

⁹ Ibid, Section 46.

¹⁰ The Tanzania Regulatory Authority Act, No. 12 of 2003.

¹¹ The Tanzania Regulatory Authority Act, No. 12 of 2003.

¹² The Tanzania Regulatory Authority Act, No. 12 of 2003.

enforcement, leading to overlapping roles and occasional coordination challenges with COSOTA.

3.2.4 The Cybercrimes Act, Cap. 443 [RE 2023]

The Cybercrimes Act was enacted to combat offenses committed through computer systems and digital networks. It criminalizes activities such as illegal access to computer systems, data interference, and online fraud—all of which can affect the security and integrity of digital artistic works. The Act also provides for the collection and admissibility of electronic evidence, which is crucial for prosecuting online copyright infringements. Although the Cybercrimes Act does not specifically target copyright violations, its provisions complement copyright law by protecting digital platforms and electronic data from unauthorized manipulation. By prescribing penalties for cyber offenses, the Act creates a deterrent environment for individuals who might seek to illegally copy or distribute digital artistic works.

3.2.5 Electronic Transactions Act, Cap. 442 [RE 2023]

The Electronic Transactions Act provides legal recognition for electronic transactions, e-signatures, and digital documents in Tanzania.¹³ For artists, this Act is particularly significant because it legitimizes online contracts, digital sales, and e-commerce transactions related to their works. It also allows electronic evidence to be used in court, which is essential for resolving disputes over online copyright infringement.¹⁴ In the digital economy, where artists often distribute their works through websites, streaming platforms, and social media, this Act ensures that their electronic dealings are legally binding and enforceable. Although it does not directly regulate artistic content, it strengthens the broader legal ecosystem for protecting creative works traded or shared online.¹⁵

3.3 Institutional framework

At the institutional level, the Copyright Society of Tanzania (COSOTA) is the central authority for managing and enforcing copyright protection. COSOTA operates under the Ministry of Culture, Arts, and Sports, and works closely with other entities such as the Tanzania Communications Regulatory Authority (TCRA), law enforcement agencies, and the judiciary to enforce copyright laws. In practice, COSOTA's effectiveness in the ICT era is constrained by limited resources, inadequate digital infrastructure, and weak coordination with international copyright enforcement systems. The institution lacks advanced digital monitoring tools and has no formal agreements with global platforms like YouTube or Spotify, making it difficult to track and act upon digital infringements originating beyond Tanzania's borders.

¹³ The Electronic Transaction Act, Cap. 442 [RE 2023].

¹⁴ The Electronic Transaction Act, Cap. 442 [RE 2023].

¹⁵ The Electronic Transaction Act, Cap. 442 [RE 2023].

Nevertheless, COSOTA continues to play an important role in raising awareness, licensing music and audiovisual works, and representing Tanzanian creators in regional and international forums. Strengthening its technological capacity and fostering inter-agency cooperation are critical steps toward building a more responsive institutional framework for digital copyright enforcement.

4. Legal and institutional challenges in the digital era

4.1 Need to review legal provisions, and lack of digital-specific policy

Tanzania's copyright legislation, primarily the Copyright and Neighbouring Rights Act, Cap. 218 [RE 2023], provides the foundational framework for protecting creative and artistic works. However, the Act was originally enacted in 1999 before the widespread use of the internet and social media and therefore does not adequately address the complexities of protecting artistic works in the digital environment. While it recognizes moral and economic rights, it lacks provisions that deal specifically with digital reproduction, online distribution, streaming, or peer-to-peer file sharing.¹⁶

Technologies that are raising issues for copyright law are those related to digital storage and transmission of works. The aspects of these technologies that have implications for copyright law include those which make it easy to reproduce and disseminate protected works. Once a work is rendered in digital form, it can be reproduced rapidly, at little cost and without loss of quality. Each copy can further be reproduced without any loss of quality.¹⁷ Similarly, the emergence of global digital networks allows rapid dissemination of work in digital form worldwide. Thus, technological developments have made copyright material easier to access and reproduce but more difficult to protect.

Tanzania Copyrights and Neighbouring Rights Act¹⁸ provides a foundational framework for protecting artistic works, including music, films, visual arts, and folklore, through provisions for economic rights¹⁹ and moral rights²⁰ under the Act. However, this Act, enacted before the massive growth of information and communication, lacks digital-specific provisions to address the challenges posed by the digital era, such as online reproduction, distribution, and modification of artistic works. This absence is particularly detrimental in Tanzania's technological landscape and artistic rights.²¹ The Act focuses more on pre-digital context, focusing on physical media such as books, CDs, and VHS tapes. Its provisions do not explicitly address the unique characteristics of digital

¹⁶ <https://www.ippmedia.com/the-guardian/sports/football/read/cosota-urged-to-clamp-down-on-content-piracy-2024-04-12-094439>

¹⁷ Grace N, (2016) 'The Challenges of ICT Development with Regards to Copyright Protection in Tanzania,' *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology* (IJERT), (2016 Vol. 5) 91.

¹⁸ The Copyright and Neighbouring Rights Act, Cap. 218 RE 2023;

¹⁹ Section 9 of the Copyright and Neighbouring Rights Act Cap 218 (RE 2023).

²⁰ Ibid, Section 11

²¹ Ibid, Section 10

technologies, such as Online Reproduction and Distribution, including the rapid, low-cost reproduction and global dissemination of digital works via the internet, with platforms like YouTube.

Also, the Act lacks intermediary liability rules to hold online platforms accountable for hosting infringing content, such as takedown procedures or content filtering. Again, the Act does not address unauthorized alterations of digital works on social media (e.g., TikTok edits), which affect moral rights. Peer-to-peer sharing is not captured by the Act on file-sharing technologies such as WhatsApp and Telegram, where artistic works are distributed without permission.

Other shortcomings of the Act lie in its area of enforcement²² which focuses on physical seizures, civil remedies (e.g., injunctions), and criminal penalties (e.g., fines, imprisonment), but lack mechanisms for digital monitoring, automated takedowns, or cross-border enforcement. This contrasts with TRIPS Articles 41–61, which mandate effective enforcement, including in digital contexts. The impact of the lack of digital-specific provisions, among others, results in economic loss by creators who lose millions annually due to unaddressed digital piracy.

This legislative gap has created vulnerabilities for Tanzanian creators whose works are shared, remixed, or monetized online without authorization. Digital platforms such as YouTube, TikTok, and Instagram have become key outlets for artistic expression, yet Tanzania's legal framework does not provide clear mechanisms to regulate or enforce copyright on these platforms. The absence of a dedicated national policy on digital or creative industries further exacerbates the issue, as there is no coherent strategy guiding the protection, commercialization, and enforcement of digital artistic rights. Consequently, the outdated legal framework struggles to keep pace with the rapid technological evolution that shapes the creation and consumption of art today.

4.2 Inadequate enforcement of moral and economic rights

Although Tanzanian law recognizes both moral and economic rights of artists, the enforcement of these rights remains weak especially in the digital space.²³ Moral rights, such as the right of attribution and the right to preserve the integrity of a work, are often violated when artistic content is reposted, altered, or misattributed on digital platforms. For example, a visual artist's digital painting may be reproduced or edited by another user without credit or consent, undermining the artist's reputation and creative integrity.

²² Ibid, Section 37

²³ <https://www.ippmedia.com/the-guardian/sports/football/read/cosota-urged-to-clamp-down-on-content-piracy-2024-04-12-094439>

Economic rights are similarly undermined by the proliferation of online piracy and unauthorized reproductions.²⁴ Enforcement agencies, such as the Copyright Society of Tanzania (COSOTA), lack the technological and human capacity to detect and act on infringements that occur on global online platforms. As a result, artists are deprived of revenue and control over their creations, while infringers continue to exploit their works with minimal risk of legal consequences. The gap between the legal recognition of rights and their practical enforcement highlights a critical shortfall in Tanzania's copyright regime in the ICT era.

4.3 Limited monitoring capacity and technological infrastructure

Effective copyright protection in the digital age requires robust technological systems for monitoring and enforcing intellectual property rights online. Tanzania currently lacks such infrastructure.²⁵ COSOTA and related enforcement agencies rely largely on manual complaint-based systems, which are insufficient for detecting the vast number of potential infringements occurring on digital platforms daily. Unlike developed jurisdictions that use digital rights management tools, automated takedown systems, and monitoring software, Tanzania's institutions operate with limited financial and technical resources. This incapacity prevents real time surveillance of digital platforms and weakens deterrence against infringement. The absence of collaboration between regulatory authorities such as COSOTA, TCRA, and international online platforms further compounds enforcement challenges. Without significant investment in digital infrastructure and inter-agency cooperation, monitoring and protecting artistic works in cyberspace will remain largely ineffective

4.4 Non-ratification of treaties

The failure to ratify and domesticate these treaties limits Tanzania's ability to engage in international cooperation for the enforcement of digital copyright. Consequently, when Tanzanian artistic works—such as music, films, or digital art—are infringed abroad, artists often lack legal recourse or institutional support to pursue remedies.²⁶ This non-ratification also hinders access to modern digital-rights-management systems and regional enforcement networks, placing Tanzanian creators at a disadvantage in the global digital marketplace.

4.5 Jurisdictional and ownership challenges in cyberspace

The global and decentralized nature of cyberspace poses complex jurisdictional challenges for copyright enforcement. Infringements of Tanzanian artistic works frequently occur on servers hosted outside the country, making it difficult to determine

²⁴ The Copyright and Neighbouring Rights Act, CAP. 218 (RE 2023);

²⁵ <https://www.ippmedia.com/the-guardian/sports/football/read/cosota-urged-to-clamp-down-on-content-piracy-2024-04-12-094439>

²⁶ <https://www.ippmedia.com/the-guardian/sports/football/read/cosota-urged-to-clamp-down-on-content-piracy-2024-04-12-094439>

which court has authority to adjudicate the matter.²⁷ Even when infringing content is identified, tracing the perpetrator or securing cooperation from foreign digital platforms can be cumbersome and costly.

Ownership disputes further complicate the protection of artistic works in digital spaces. Online platforms often host user generated content where multiple parties such as producers, performers, and distributors may claim partial rights. The lack of digital registration systems in Tanzania makes it difficult to verify original ownership or establish the chain of title for artistic works. This uncertainty weakens enforcement and allows infringers to exploit legal ambiguities, leading to loss of control and revenue for artists.

4.6 Limited expertise and public awareness

Another major constraint in protecting artistic works in the ICT era is the shortage of professionals with expertise in digital copyright and cyber-law enforcement.²⁸ Many legal practitioners, judicial officers, and policymakers lack specialized knowledge of emerging technologies and their implications for intellectual property protection. This results in procedural delays, evidentiary challenges, and inconsistent judicial interpretations of digital infringement cases. Equally concerning is the low level of public awareness among artists and consumers regarding copyright rights and obligations. Many creators are unaware of how to register their works with COSOTA or how to report online infringements, while consumers often engage in unauthorized sharing and downloading without understanding the legal implications.²⁹ Public education and training programs on intellectual property remain limited. Without targeted awareness campaigns and capacity-building initiatives, the protection of artistic works in the digital environment will continue to face significant setbacks.

4.7 Failure to address cross-border piracy

Cross-border piracy is governed by the WIPO³⁰ Performances and Phonograms Treaty (WPPT, 1996)³¹, and the African Regional Intellectual Property Organization (ARIPO)'s and The Kampala Protocol on Voluntary Registration of Copyright and Related Rights (2021)³². It is unfortunate that, Tanzania has not ratified these key international and regional instruments. Tanzania has made a step by signing the protocol, it has not yet ratified it, meaning it has not formally deposited the instrument of ratification with ARIPO to make it legally binding, this has significant negative impacts on the protection of artistic works, particularly in the digital era. This non-ratification perpetuates gaps in

²⁷ Seth K, *Computers Internet and New Technology Laws* (LexisNexis, Haryana. 2013, 1st edition) 223

²⁸ Ibid.

²⁹ Ibid.

³⁰ Seth K, *Computers Internet and New Technology Laws* (LexisNexis, Haryana. 2013, 1st edition) 223

³¹ Article 15

³² Article 3

Tanzania's Copyright and Neighbouring Rights³³ by hindering effective enforcement against online infringement, limiting access to modern tools like digital rights management (DRM) and weakening regional cooperation.

The lack of a multilateral framework means Tanzanian content remains unprotected on regional platforms, where piracy thrives due to inconsistent enforcement, costing creators significant revenue estimated at millions of shillings annually.³⁴ This gap enables cross-border exploitation, with Tanzanian artists losing both moral rights and economic rights as platforms prioritize claims from countries with established agreements. Studies indicate that while Tanzania is legally bound by international copyright standards, the absence of comprehensive policies and mechanisms for cross-border enforcement means that Tanzanian creators often face challenges when their works are infringed upon abroad.³⁵

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

The rapid expansion of digital technologies has transformed the creation, distribution, and consumption of artistic works in Tanzania, presenting both opportunities and challenges. While the country possesses foundational copyright laws and institutional frameworks through COSOTA, these mechanisms remain largely tailored to traditional media and struggle to address the complexities of the digital environment. Weak enforcement, limited technical capacity, and lack of public awareness have left artists vulnerable to online piracy, unauthorized use, and revenue loss.

To effectively safeguard artistic works, Tanzania must modernize its legal framework, strengthen institutional capacity, and align with international standards such as WIPO treaties and ARIPO protocols. Building technical expertise among artists and authorities, coupled with collaboration with global digital platforms, will ensure creators can fully realize the economic and moral rights of their works. Ultimately, protecting artistic works in the ICT era is not just a legal imperative but a strategic investment in Tanzania's cultural economy, creativity, and international visibility. By bridging gaps between law, technology, and public awareness, Tanzania can create a vibrant, sustainable environment where artistic innovation thrives and artists are fairly rewarded for their contributions.

³³ Cap. 218 (RE 2023)

³⁴ Seth K, *Computers Internet and New Technology Laws* (LexisNexis, Haryana. 2013, 1st edition) 223

³⁵ Grace N, (2016) 'The Challenges of ICT Development with Regards to Copyright Protection in Tanzania,' *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology* (IJERT), (2016 Vol. 5) 92.

5.2 Recommendations

Tanzania's current Copyright Act was originally designed for traditional media and physical forms of artistic works. With the rise of digital content creation and online distribution (music streaming, online galleries, video platforms), the law struggles to address issues like: Online piracy and illegal downloading, unauthorized remixing or adaptation of digital art, licensing and royalties for works distributed via digital platforms and updating the Act would explicitly cover digital reproductions, online transmissions, streaming, and cloud storage, giving artists clear legal recourse against infringement in the ICT environment. This would also provide clarity on rights management, fair use, and digital licensing agreements.

COSOTA is the main institution managing copyright protection and royalties in Tanzania. However, in the digital era, it faces challenges such as inability to track online use of artistic works, limited technological tools for monitoring digital piracy and difficulty in enforcing copyright on global online platforms. Strengthening COSOTA would involve investing in digital rights management (DRM) systems, training staff on ICT-based monitoring and enforcement and enhancing coordination with law enforcement and regulatory bodies. This would ensure artists are adequately compensated and protected in a digital market.

Tanzania has not ratified important international treaties such as: WIPO Copyright Treaty (WCT), WIPO Performances and Phonograms Treaty (WPPT) and ARIPO Kampala Protocol on Copyright and Related Rights. Ratification would align Tanzania with global standards for online copyright protection. Enable enforcement of Tanzanian artists' rights abroad and facilitate participation in regional and international digital rights management systems. This ensures Tanzanian artists are protected internationally when their works are shared online.

Digital platforms like YouTube, Spotify, TikTok, and social media sites are now primary channels for artistic distribution. Without formal collaboration, Tanzanian artists face unlicensed use of their content and loss of revenue from global streams or downloads. Encouraging collaboration means; establishing partnerships with streaming platforms to automatically track and monetize Tanzanian works. Participating in global digital rights management systems for cross-border protection and ensuring proper licensing agreements are in place to secure royalties. This integrates Tanzanian artistic works into the global digital economy, increasing visibility and revenue opportunities.